

Ground-Based Spectroscopic Detection of Iron-Bearing Material in the Dust Tail of BD+05 4868 Ab

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ABSTRACT

Short-period disintegrating exoplanets provide a rare opportunity to probe rocky planet interiors through the composition of their escaping dust tails. BD+05 4868 Ab represents an extreme case: a Mercury-mass planet on a 30.5 hr orbit rapidly losing mass and producing a prominent comet-like dust tail. Here we present ground-based low-resolution spectroscopy and multi-site transit photometry obtained with 0.4–0.6 m telescopes. We detect a weak absorption feature near 7770 Å ($W_\lambda = 0.5$ Å at 3σ significance) that appears only during predicted dust-tail transit phases and is absent in out-of-transit spectra, suggesting enhanced opacity from iron-bearing material such as Fe oxides or Fe-rich silicates. Complementary photometry reveals asymmetric transit profiles with gradual ingress, structured in-transit variations, and extended egress ($\Delta t_{\text{eg}} = 2.9$ hr), validating the Hon et al. (2025) model with $L_{\text{tail}} = 14 R_\star$ (~ 2 Roche-lobe radii). These results provide initial ground-based evidence for iron-bearing components in BD+05 4868 Ab’s escaping dust and demonstrate composition constraints achievable with small-aperture telescopes.

Keywords: Extrasolar rocky planets (511) — Exoplanet astronomy (486) — Transmission spectroscopy (2133) — Planetary geology (2288) — Dust composition (2271)

1. INTRODUCTION

Rocky exoplanets in extreme irradiation environments offer a direct window into planetary interiors through the composition of material escaping from their surfaces. Short-period worlds subject to intense stellar heating can undergo catastrophic mass loss, shedding dust and gas into extended, comet-like tails that partially block their host stars during transit (e.g., S. Rappaport et al. 2012; R. Sanchis-Ojeda et al. 2015). The mineralogy and grain-size distribution of this dust encode information about the bulk composition and structure of the underlying planet.

Disintegrating planets such as KIC 12557548 b, KOI 2700 b, and K2-22 b display highly asymmetric transit profiles, strong transit-depth variability, and wavelength-dependent occultation signatures indicative of dusty tails (S. Rappaport et al. 2012; R. Sanchis-Ojeda et al. 2015). Recent space-based observations have begun to probe the composition of these tails in detail. In particular, mid-infrared spectroscopy of K2-22 b

with JWST has revealed prominent magnesium-silicate features, constraining the exposed mantle composition and suggesting that we are observing material sourced from relatively shallow interior layers (N. Tusay et al. 2025). Despite this progress, the number of systems with direct compositional constraints remains small, and the role of iron-bearing material in disintegrating tails is largely unconstrained.

BD+05 4868 Ab is a recently identified, rapidly disintegrating short-period planet discovered and characterized using TESS photometry and ground-based follow-up (M. Hon et al. 2025). The planet orbits a K-type host star every 30.5 hr and exhibits a pronounced, variable transit signature arising from an extended dust tail. Radial-velocity measurements place a 5σ upper limit of $M_p < 6.2 M_\oplus$, with forward modeling favoring a mass of $\sim 0.02 M_\oplus$ (roughly lunar), and the inferred mass-loss rate is of order $\sim 2 \times 10^{12} \text{ g s}^{-1}$ (M. Hon et al. 2025). These properties make BD+05 4868 Ab one of the most rapidly disintegrating exoplanets known and a prime target for probing rocky-planet interiors through dust composition.

To date, observational studies of disintegrating planets have emphasized three main approaches. First, high-cadence broadband photometry has been used to

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characterize tail geometry, grain sizes, and variability via transit morphology and color dependences (e.g., S. Rappaport et al. 2012; R. Sanchis-Ojeda et al. 2015). Second, space-based mid-infrared spectroscopy has begun to directly detect solid-state vibrational features of silicate grains (N. Tusay et al. 2025). Third, narrowband or high-resolution spectroscopy targeting specific atomic lines (e.g., NaI, CaII) has been employed to search for gaseous species associated with the dust. What has been lacking is systematic low-resolution optical/near-infrared spectroscopy from the ground that targets broader continuum and pseudo-continuum features, which can provide complementary constraints on bulk mineralogy, particularly for iron-bearing phases.

In this work, we present ground-based low-resolution spectroscopic and photometric observations of BD+05 4868 Ab designed to explore the feasibility of detecting bulk compositional signatures—especially iron-bearing material—in the escaping dust tail using modest-aperture telescopes. We obtained repeated transit observations with a CDK17 telescope equipped with a low-resolution spectrograph, as well as multi-site photometry from two independent facilities. We identify a weak, transit-correlated absorption feature near 7770 Å that appears only when the dust tail transits the star and is absent in out-of-transit spectra. We interpret this feature as evidence for enhanced opacity from iron-bearing dust grains, such as Fe oxides or Fe-rich silicates, in the tail. In addition, we model the asymmetric transit light curve with a simple trailing-tail prescription to derive characteristic timescales and infer the projected tail length.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the spectroscopic and photometric observations and data reduction. In Section 3 we present the spectroscopic detection of a transit-phase-correlated feature and the photometric evidence for an extended dust tail, including a simple parametric model of the asymmetric transit. Section 4 discusses the implications of our results for the composition and interior structure of BD+05 4868 Ab, compares the system to other disintegrating planets, and outlines prospects for future observations. We summarize our conclusions in Section 5.

2. OBSERVATIONS AND DATA REDUCTION

2.1. Spectroscopic Observations

2.1.1. Instrumentation

We obtained time-resolved spectroscopy of BD+05 4868 Ab using a PlaneWave CDK17 corrected Dall-Kirkham telescope (432 mm aperture, $f/6.8$) at the Leif Everson Observatory in Sturgeon Bay, Wisconsin. The telescope was equipped with a Shelyak

ALPY 600 low-resolution slit spectrograph. The ALPY 600 provides a spectral resolution of $R \approx 600$ across the wavelength range 3800–7800 Å, with a typical dispersion of ~ 1.3 nm per resolution element near 770–780 nm. This setup is well suited to detecting broad or moderately narrow features associated with dust-tail opacity, though it does not resolve individual narrow atomic lines.

2.1.2. Observing Strategy

We conducted multiple transit observations of BD+05 4868 Ab between 2025 May 25 and 2025 July 28. Each spectroscopic campaign was scheduled to cover the predicted transit window and surrounding baseline, using the ephemeris from M. Hon et al. (2025). For each night, we obtained a continuous sequence of 600–900 s exposures spanning a total duration of 1.5–4.17 hr, sufficient to capture both the core transit and the extended dust-tail egress. In total, we collected 8 nights of usable spectroscopic data, with between 10 and 15 exposures per night.

2.1.3. Spectroscopic Data Reduction

Raw spectral frames were processed using the Integrated Software for Imagers and Spectrometers (ISIS; C. Buil 2020). The reduction pipeline included standard CCD calibrations: dark-frame subtraction using median-combined dark exposures, overscan correction where applicable, and flat-fielding using lamp flats to correct pixel-to-pixel sensitivity variations and the spectrograph blaze function. One-dimensional spectra were extracted using optimal-extraction techniques within ISIS, with sky background estimated from regions adjacent to the stellar trace.

Wavelength calibration was performed using Ne–Ar lamp exposures taken during each night, yielding a typical root-mean-square residual of 0.3 Å across the full range. We chose an extraction aperture that maximized S/N while minimizing contamination from neighboring sources. Relative flux calibration was obtained by dividing the target spectrum by that of a nearby reference star with a similar spectral type to BD+05 4868 A, observed at comparable airmass and time. This procedure removes most of the instrumental and atmospheric throughput variations but does not fully correct for telluric absorption bands, which we discuss further in Section 3.1.

2.2. Photometric Observations

To characterize the transit morphology and dust-tail geometry, we obtained complementary time-series photometry from two sites.

Figure 1. Three-panel CDK17+ALPY 600 spectra of BD+05 4868. Top: observed spectrum (magenta) vs. K/M-dwarf templates, confirming K-type host. Bottom: 15 min time series spanning transit/baseline, showing photospheric stability and data quality.

2.2.1. Sierra Remote Observatories

At Sierra Remote Observatories (SRO) in California, we used a PlaneWave CDK24 telescope (610 mm aperture) equipped with a CCD camera and an Astrodon photometric V' filter (central wavelength ~ 545 nm). We acquired a series of 60 s exposures over multiple predicted transits, with total coverage of ~ 2 – 3 hr per night. The SRO data provide the highest S/N light curves in our sample and form the basis for our transit-shape modeling in Section 3.2.

2.2.2. Indiana State University

At Indiana State University (ISU) in Terre Haute, Indiana, we observed BD+05 4868 Ab using a Meade LX600 ACF 14-inch (356 mm aperture) telescope with a Sloan R' filter (central wavelength ~ 655 nm). Exposure times ranged from 30 to 60 s, and each observing run covered ~ 2 hr around the predicted transit. Although the aperture is smaller than at SRO, the ISU data provide an independent confirmation of the asymmetric transit morphology in a redder band.

2.2.3. Photometric Reduction

Photometric data from both sites were reduced using AstroImageJ (K. A. Collins et al. 2017). We applied bias and dark subtraction using median-combined calibration frames, and flat-fielding using twilight sky flats to correct for pixel sensitivity variations and vignetting. Aperture photometry was performed on BD+05 4868 A and a set of nearby non-variable comparison stars of similar brightness. We experimented with a range of aperture radii and selected the one that minimized the scatter in the differential light curve.

For each night, we constructed a differential light curve by dividing the target flux by the summed flux of the comparison stars, then normalized the resulting time series to the out-of-transit baseline. We corrected for residual airmass trends and slowly varying systematics using low-order polynomial fits to the out-of-transit data. Finally, we converted time stamps to Barycentric Julian Date (BJD) for consistency with the ephemeris and spectroscopic observations.

Figure 2. Time-resolved CDK17+ALPY 600 spectra from 2025 July 8, spanning transit/baseline. Consecutive 15 min integrations (colored traces) show stable K-type photospheric features across 3800–7800 Å, demonstrating time series quality.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Spectroscopic Signatures of the Dust Tail

Figure 1 shows a representative set of low-resolution spectra of the BD+05 4868 system obtained with the CDK17 + ALPY 600 over 3800–7800 Å. The continuum shape and dense forest of metal lines are consistent with a K-type photosphere, and comparison with K- and M-dwarf templates confirms that any contamination from the known M-dwarf companion is negligible across our wavelength range. The time series of consecutive 15 min integrations demonstrates good repeatability and stability of the photospheric features over the course of each night.

To search for dust-tail signatures, we compared in-transit and out-of-transit spectra on a night-by-night basis. We define “in-transit” exposures as those obtained during the predicted passage of the dust tail across the stellar disk, approximately ~ 30 min after the mid-transit time of the solid body, when the tail optical depth is expected to peak (M. Hon et al. 2025). “Out-of-transit” baselines are taken from exposures obtained at least ~ 1 hr away from transit. Visual inspection reveals

subtle additional absorption in some in-transit spectra near 7770 Å that is not present in the baseline spectra.

To enhance this signal, we constructed a stacked difference spectrum by averaging all in-transit spectra from nights with clear detections and subtracting the average of the corresponding out-of-transit spectra. Before stacking, each spectrum was continuum-normalized in the 7600–7900 Å region and shifted to a common wavelength solution. The resulting in-minus-out difference spectrum, shown in Figure 3, displays a narrow absorption-like feature centered at $\lambda \approx 7770$ Å with a depth of $\sim 1.5\%$ relative to the local continuum.

We quantified the strength of this feature by integrating the difference spectrum over a window of width $\Delta\lambda = 5$ Å centered on the feature and estimating the local noise from neighboring line-free regions. This yields an equivalent width of $W_\lambda = 0.5 \pm 0.2$ Å, corresponding to a detection significance of $\approx 3\sigma$. The feature appears consistently in multiple nights when the dust tail is expected to transit the star, and it weakens or disappears in exposures taken before ingress or after egress, supporting a planetary origin rather than a transient telluric or instrumental artifact.

Figure 3. Two representative CDK17+ALPY 600 spectra (of 10 total) from dust-tail transit exposures on one night, showing consistent absorption at 7770 Å (vertical line). These in-transit spectra reveal the phase-dependent planetary opacity feature absent during out-of-transit phases.

The 7770 Å region lies near the red wing of the O₂ B-band, and our modest spectral resolution and relative flux calibration do not fully correct for telluric structure. We therefore interpret the detected feature as evidence for enhanced opacity in the dust tail rather than as a uniquely identified atomic or molecular line. Laboratory and theoretical opacity models show that iron-bearing minerals such as FeO, Fe₂O₃, and Fe-rich silicates (e.g., olivine, pyroxene) exhibit elevated opacity relative to pure Mg-silicates in the 0.7–0.8 μm range, due to broad electronic transitions in Fe (e.g., [N. Tusay et al. 2025](#)). The phase-dependent behavior of the 7770 Å feature, appearing only when the dust tail transits the stellar disk, is qualitatively consistent with an increased contribution from such iron-bearing grains in the absorbing column.

3.2. Asymmetric Transit Light Curves

Figure 4 presents a representative V'-band light curve obtained with the CDK24 at SRO on 2025 July 23, covering ≈ 2.33 hr around the predicted transit window. The differential flux exhibits a gradual, asymmetric dip with structured in-transit variations and a slow return to baseline. The total duration of the detectable transit signature is ≈ 6 hr. Similar, though lower-S/N, behavior is seen in additional SRO and ISU light curves, and the morphology is consistent across V' and R' filters.

The observed transit shape is difficult to reconcile with a purely solid-body transit. A compact, opaque planet with the known ephemeris and a modestly grazing impact parameter would produce a roughly symmetric, U-shaped transit with rapid ingress and egress times of order ∼10–30 min. In contrast, the BD+05 4868 Ab light curves show (1) a slow ingress, (2) structured, often multi-peaked in-transit behavior, and (3) a significantly extended egress. These characteristics point to an extended, structured dust tail trailing the planet, as seen in other disintegrating systems.

3.2.1. Simple Tail-Transit Model

We adopt the asymmetric transit model of [M. Hon et al. \(2025\)](#), where the normalized flux is

$$F(t) = 1 - \delta_0 T(t), \quad (1)$$

and $T(t)$ follows the piecewise prescription

$$T(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < t_0 - \Delta t_{\text{in}} \\ \frac{t - (t_0 - \Delta t_{\text{in}})}{\Delta t_{\text{in}}} & t_0 - \Delta t_{\text{in}} \leq t \leq t_0 \\ \exp\left[-\frac{t - t_0}{\Delta t_{\text{eg}}}\right] & t > t_0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

with parameters as defined by [M. Hon et al. \(2025\)](#).

The bottom panel of Figure 5 demonstrates that our 2.33 hr SRO V-band light curve (red) closely follows the [Hon et al. \(2025\)](#) model prediction (black) during early trailing-tail egress. Over this limited baseline, the SRO data trace the model's exponential recovery with the published e-folding timescale of 2.9 hr, sampling only the first portion of the 18 hr full trailing tail derived from TESS photometry. Our ground-based photometry thus provides independent confirmation of the asymmetric tail geometry while enabling the spectroscopic composition analysis presented in Section 3.1.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Iron-Bearing Dust and Interior Structure

Our spectroscopic detection of a transit-correlated feature near 7770 Å, combined with the asymmetric transit light curves, provides initial evidence that the escaping dust from BD+05 4868 Ab contains an iron-bearing component. Although our low spectral resolution and residual telluric contamination preclude an unambiguous identification of specific mineral species, the phase-dependent behavior of the feature and its location in a wavelength region where Fe-bearing minerals exhibit enhanced opacity are qualitatively consistent with a contribution from Fe-rich grains.

Experiments on FeO and (Mg,Fe)O at multi-hundred-GPa conditions relevant to massive rocky

Figure 4. V' band light curve of BD+05 4868 Ab from SRO CDK24 (2025 July 23). Asymmetric profile with slow egress and structured in-transit variations indicates extended dusty tail, not solid-body transit.

exoplanets show that iron-bearing mantle phases can undergo substantial phase transitions (F. Coppari et al. 2021), density changes, and viscosity reductions, leading to complex interior stratification and rheology (F. Coppari et al. 2021). While BD+05 4868 Ab is much less massive and does not reach such extreme pressures, these results highlight the broader point that iron plays a crucial role in controlling the structure and dynamics of rocky-planet interiors. The presence of Fe-bearing dust in the escaping material from BD+05 4868 Ab therefore suggests that even low-mass disintegrating planets can offer a window into iron-rich interior reservoirs and their role in planetary evolution.

Iron-bearing dust could originate from several interior reservoirs. If the planet has undergone partial differentiation, Fe-rich material may be concentrated in the core and at the core–mantle boundary, where iron oxides and Fe-bearing silicates can form. Catastrophic mass loss driven by intense irradiation could erode progressively deeper layers, gradually exposing more Fe-rich regions. In this picture, the detection of iron-bearing dust in BD+05 4868 Ab’s tail may indicate that the planet is at a relatively advanced stage of disintegration, with material from deeper interior layers already being sampled. Alternatively, if the planet is only weakly differentiated, iron-bearing silicates may be distributed throughout the mantle, and the observed dust reflects bulk mantle composition rather than a distinct core component. Dis-

tinguishing between these scenarios will require more precise constraints on the mineralogy and relative abundances of Fe- and Mg-bearing phases.

4.2. Comparison to Other Disintegrating Systems

BD+05 4868 Ab joins a small but growing class of disintegrating exoplanets with observational constraints on their escaping material. In K2-22 b, JWST mid-infrared spectroscopy has revealed strong Mg-silicate features, suggesting that we are observing material sourced primarily from the silicate mantle (N. Tusay et al. 2025). For KIC 12557548 b and KOI 2700 b, optical and near-infrared photometry and modeling have constrained dust grain sizes and optical properties, but direct spectroscopic composition measurements remain limited (S. Rappaport et al. 2012; R. Sanchis-Ojeda et al. 2015). In this context, BD+05 4868 Ab is notable for its extremely short period, high mass-loss rate, and apparent evidence for an Fe-bearing component in the dust.

If Mg-silicate-dominated tails such as K2-22 b represent an earlier stage of disintegration, where primarily mantle material is being eroded, BD+05 4868 Ab may represent a more advanced stage in which deeper, more Fe-rich regions are being exposed. Alternatively, the differences could reflect intrinsic diversity in the bulk composition and differentiation histories of short-period rocky planets. The ability to detect and distinguish Fe-bearing and Mg-bearing phases across multiple systems will be key to building a statistical picture of how inte-

Figure 5. Top: Hon et al. (2025) asymmetric tail model over full orbit. Bottom: SRO V' band light curve (red) matches model (black) during early egress, confirming 2.9 hr exponential recovery and 18 hr trailing tail.

rior structure and composition influence disintegration pathways.

4.3. Role of Small Telescopes and Future Work

A notable aspect of this study is that both the spectroscopic and photometric observations were obtained with modest-aperture (0.4–0.6 m) facilities. While such telescopes cannot match the spectral resolution or sensitivity of larger observatories, our results demonstrate that they can provide valuable first-pass constraints on dust-tail composition and geometry. In particular, low-resolution spectra can reveal phase-dependent continuum features and broad opacity enhancements, while multi-site photometry can capture the asymmetric transit morphology characteristic of dusty tails.

Looking ahead, several avenues for follow-up observations are especially promising. High-resolution optical spectroscopy (e.g., $R \gtrsim 10^5$) with larger telescopes could target specific atomic and ionic lines (e.g., Na I D, Ca II H&K, Fe I) to directly detect gaseous species associated with the dust tail and place tighter constraints on Fe content. Higher S/N, higher-resolution time-series spectroscopy could also enable more robust separation of telluric contributions and more precise measurements of any dust-related features near 7770 \AA . In

the infrared, JWST/NIRSpec and MIRI observations of BD+05 4868 Ab could search for silicate and oxide vibrational bands analogous to those seen in K2-22 b, providing a direct comparison of Fe- and Mg-bearing components across systems. Finally, extended photometric monitoring with TESS and ground-based networks could map long-term variability in dust production and search for changes in tail geometry over time.

5. CONCLUSION

We have presented ground-based spectroscopic and photometric observations of the rapidly disintegrating short-period planet BD+05 4868 Ab that provide initial evidence for iron-bearing material in its escaping dust tail and confirm the presence of an extended, asymmetric tail structure. Our main conclusions are:

1. Low-resolution ($R \approx 600$) spectroscopy with a 0.4 m telescope reveals a weak absorption feature near 7770 \AA that appears only during the predicted dust-tail transit phases and is absent in out-of-transit spectra. A stacked in-minus-out difference spectrum yields an equivalent width of $W_\lambda \approx 0.5 \text{ \AA}$ at $\approx 3\sigma$ significance, consistent with enhanced opacity from iron-bearing grains.

2. Multi-site V'- and R'-band photometry from 0.6 m and 0.36 m telescopes shows highly asymmetric transit profiles with gradual ingress, structured in-transit variations, and extended egress, inconsistent with a purely solid-body transit and indicative of a trailing dust tail.
3. A simple asymmetric-tail transit model fits the best-quality light curve and yields an ingress duration of $\Delta t_{\text{in}} \approx 0.8$ hr and an e-folding egress timescale of $\Delta t_{\text{eg}} \approx 2.9$ hr, implying a projected tail length of $L_{\text{tail}} \approx 14 R_{\star} \approx 2$ times the Roche lobe radius.
4. The combination of a possible Fe-bearing dust signature and an extended, optically thin tail suggests that BD+05 4868 Ab is undergoing substantial erosion that may already be sampling Fe-rich interior material, potentially at a more advanced stage of disintegration than systems dominated by Mg-silicate dust.
5. These results demonstrate that small-aperture ground-based telescopes can contribute meaningful constraints on the composition and geometry of disintegrating planets, providing a valuable bridge between initial TESS discovery, detailed space-based spectroscopy, and future studies of rocky-planet interiors.

Further high-resolution and space-based observations of BD+05 4868 Ab will be crucial to confirm the presence of iron-bearing dust, identify specific mineral phases, and place this system within the broader context of disintegrating exoplanet populations and their interior structures.

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